

SUPPLEMENTAL MATERIALS

**Governance Fit between Tacit and Explicit Knowledge for
Cooperation in International Construction:
A Configurational Analysis**

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Supplemental material S1. Literature review on measurement items

References	Cooperation	Explicit knowledge transfer	Tacit knowledge transfer	Contractual governance	Relational governance	Project complexity	Environmental uncertainty
Bakhshi et al. (2016)						√	
Benítez-Ávila et al. (2018)				√	√		
Cui et al. (2019)	√						
Gao et al. (2018)						√	√
Kivrak et al. (2008)		√	√				
Li et al. (2010)		√	√	√	√		
Lin et al. (2024)	√						
Lu et al. (2016)				√			
Luo et al. (2017)						√	
Mesly (2015)	√						
Mohamed (2011)							√
Muller et al. (2012)						√	
Ning (2018)				√			
Raza-Ullah (2021)	√				√		
Shu et al. (2017)	√						
ul Musawir et al. (2020)				√	√		
Yan and Zhang (2020)				√	√		
You et al. (2020)							√
Zhang et al. (2024)				√	√		
Zhang et al. (2016)				√	√		
Zhou and Deng (2025)		√	√				
Zhou et al. (2020)		√	√				

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Supplemental material S2. Questionnaire survey

Dear Sir/Madam,

Hello! Thank you very much for taking the time to help us complete this questionnaire. This survey aims to understand knowledge transfer and cooperation in international engineering projects. The questionnaire is conducted anonymously and follows the principle of voluntary participation. The collected data will be used solely for academic research purposes, and all personal information will be kept strictly confidential. There are no right or wrong answers—please respond according to your actual experience. If you have any questions or suggestions regarding this questionnaire, please feel free to contact us.

If you wish, you may leave your address and contact information at the end of the questionnaire, and we will mail you a complimentary book as a token of appreciation. Completing the questionnaire will take approximately 10–15 minutes. We sincerely thank you for your support and wish you success and happiness!

Part A. Basic Information

Please recall one overseas infrastructure project undertaken in the form of an international construction joint venture (ICJV) in which you have participated. Based on your actual experience of cooperation and knowledge transfer within that project, please answer the following questions.

1. **Project name:** _____
2. **Host country:** _____
3. **From which countries are the JV members?** _____
4. **Type of project:**
 - A. Road and bridge (including railway)
 - B. Port and waterway
 - C. Energy (hydropower, thermal, nuclear)
 - D. Municipal engineering
 - E. Telecommunication
 - F. Industrial projects (e.g., petrochemical)
 - G. Housing construction
 - H. Economic and trade cooperation zone
 - I. Others

5. Total investment (RMB):

- A. Less than 50 million
- B. 50–100 million
- C. 100 million–1 billion
- D. 1–3 billion
- E. More than 3 billion

6. Total project duration:

- A. Less than 2 years
- B. 2–3 years
- C. More than 3 years

7. Your position in the project:

- A. Senior executive
- B. Department manager
- C. Junior manager
- D. Professional engineer
- E. Others

8. Years of experience in overseas infrastructure project management:

- A. Less than 5 years
- B. 5–10 years
- C. 11–15 years
- D. 16–20 years
- E. More than 20 years

PART B. Cooperation

Please rate the following items based on the actual cooperation among the members within the project

(1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neutral, 7 = strongly agree).

1. Both parties often cooperate to share information in our project

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2. Both parties cooperate closely to make sure work is completed successfully

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3. Both parties contribute sufficient technological and management know-how to the work

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

4. Both parties exchange many ideas on how to improve our capabilities

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

PART C. Explicit knowledge transfer

Please rate the following items based on the actual operation of the project in relation to explicit knowledge transfer (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neutral, 7 = strongly agree).

1. We acquired written knowledge of local engineering technologies from the other party

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2. We acquired written knowledge about local operating routines and procedures from the other party

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3. We acquired written knowledge about management techniques in host country from the other party

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

PART D. Tacit knowledge transfer

Please rate the following items based on the actual operation of the project in relation to tacit knowledge transfer (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neutral, 7 = strongly agree).

1. We gained local marketing expertise that was difficult to articulate (e.g., tricks of the trade) from the other party

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2. We gained knowledge about local culture and that were not well documented from the other party

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3. We learned noncodified managerial techniques from the other party.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

PART E. Contract completeness

Please rate the following items based on the actual operation of the project in relation to contract completeness (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neutral, 7 = strongly agree).

1. The contract explicitly defines the role of each party

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2. The contract explicitly defines how each party is to perform

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3. The contract explicitly defines the specification and standards in construction

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

4. The contract explicitly defines what will happen in the case of unplanned events occurring

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

5. The contract explicitly defines how disagreements will be resolved

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

6. The contract explicitly defines the changes and adjustment clauses

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

PART F. Trust

Please rate the following items based on the actual operation of the project in relation to trust between JV partners (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neutral, 7 = strongly agree).

1. Both parties perceive the other as honest

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2. Each party believes that the other party keeps its promises all the time

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3. Both parties perceive the other as trustworthy

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

PART G. Project complexity

Please rate the following items based on the actual operation of the project in relation to project complexity (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neutral, 7 = strongly agree).

1. To overcome the technical difficulties, contributions from both parties are required

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2. To overcome the technical difficulties, a party needs to keep continuous communication with other parties

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3. The number of different tasks in this project are large compared with the industry

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

4. The number of different disciplines in this project are large compared with the industry

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

5. The number of subcontractors and suppliers in this project are large compared to the industry

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

6. The number of information transferring hierarchies in this project are large compared with the industry

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

PART H. Environmental uncertainty

Please rate the following items based on the external environment of the project in relation to

environmental uncertainty (1 = strongly disagree, 4 = neutral, 7 = strongly agree).

1. The political environment of the project is significantly unstable

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

2. The economic environment (e.g., exchange rates, raw material pricing) of the project fluctuates greatly

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

3. The project is influenced by unforeseeable geographical conditions

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

4. The project is influenced by extreme weather conditions

1 2 3 4 5 6 7

5. Predicting the future environmental condition is a real problem in the project.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7